

COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF CET COLUMNS CONSIDERING CONFINEMENT BY INNER-CFT

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1 General Introduction

Concrete-filled tube (CFT) and concrete-encased tube (CET) columns are a combination of concrete and structural steel. It is known that confinement provided by structural steel increases strength and ductility. Strength and ductility enhancements are obtained by many confinement parameters e.g., concrete compressive strength, steel yield strength, longitudinal reinforcement and the ratio of structural steel to gross area. Because of such parameters, determination of mechanical behavior of confined concrete is not as easy as unconfined concrete. So, many experimental and analytical studies have been carried out on composite columns considering confinement in the past years.

2 Experimental Investigation

An experimental investigation for the behavior of composite columns under axial compression is presented. The main objective of this investigation is to examine that confinement provided by structural steel increases strength and ductility of composite columns under axial load. For this reason, the composite columns are categorized into CFT and CET columns. These experimental results were compared with analysis results obtained by using the proposed stress-strain relation.

2.1 Test Specimens

A total of 6 test specimens were constructed and tested under axial compression. Of these 6 test specimens, three specimens were CFT columns (CFT-1,2,3) and three specimens were CET columns (CET-1,2,3). Sectional properties listed in Table 1 are the average values obtained from the tests and measurements.

Table 1. Details of test specimens

Group	L(mm)	D(mm)	t(mm)	D/t	L/D
CFT	900	325	6.34	51.3	2.8
CET	900	300	6.53	56.7	3.0

2.2 Test Procedure

Test specimens were loaded by a UTM that had the capacity of 10,000kN. This UTM makes it possible to record axial loads and axial displacements at real time with a controlling box. The photographs of test setup for CFT and CET composite columns are shown in Fig.3.

Fig.1. Configuration of CFT specimen

Fig.2. Configuration of CET specimen

(a) CFT specimen (b) CET specimen

Fig.3. Photographs of test setup

2.3 Test Results

The destruction behaviors of the CFT and CET specimens are shown in Fig.4. Test results show strength and ductility enhancement of test specimens by confined effects.

(a) CFT specimen

(b) CET specimen

Fig.4. Photographs after testing

2.4 Evaluations of test results

The experimental load-displacement relations for the CFT and CET specimens are presented in Fig.5 and Fig.6, respectively. From the test results and the code specifications, the maximum compressive strength for the specimens are listed in Table 2. These compressive strengths were compared with nominal compressive strengths, according to the ACI, AISC-LRFD and Eurocode-4 specifications. The results of the CFT and CET specimens are significantly different to those of the current code specifications. Since the current code specifications don't consider strength enhancement of confined concrete. Therefore, it is evident that analysis of composite columns was required nonlinear material properties considering confined effects. The nominal compressive strength of the ACI, the experimental and proposed maximum compressive strengths of CFT and CET specimens are shown in Fig.7 and Fig.8, respectively.

Table 2. Comparison of the compressive strength

Specimen	Experiment (kN)	Code (kN)		
		ACI	AISC-LRFD	Eurocode
CFT	4830	2732	3396	3199
CET	2610	1824	2320	2045

Fig.5. Load-displacement relations of CFT specimens

Fig.6. Load-displacement relations of CET specimens

Fig.7. Compressive strength of CFT specimens

Fig.8. Compressive strength of CET specimens

3 Behavior characteristics of CET column

Through above comparisons of the compressive strength between the CET columns and the inner CFT columns, which consisted of the concrete compressive strength of 30MPa and the steel tensile strength of 400Mpa, the strength enhancement by the confinement and the effect of cover concrete are evaluated.

Fig.9 illustrates the comparison of the compressive strength ratio for CET-to-inner CFT columns. Fig.9(a) is a graph of each strength ratio with respect to D/D_i ratios, which are the sectional parameter to investigate the effects of the cover concrete. Fig.9(b) plots the same data against the $(D-D_i)/D$ ratio, which is the sectional parameter to investigate the effects of inner CFT column.

From Fig.9, it is shown that when the thickness of the cover concrete becomes greater, the maximum compressive strength will become greater. However, in engineering construction, it is not effective that CET columns consist of the cover concrete more than 30% for the diameter of inner CFT column, due to a brittle failure that the cover concrete was suddenly spalled out.

(a) Effect of increased cover concrete

(b) Effect of inner CFT column

Fig.9. Comparison of compressive strength ratio for CET-to-inner CFT column

4 Conclusions

Nonlinear material properties considering confined effects were required for accurate analysis of composite columns. Therefore, material properties were modified after comparing the results available in the literature with the experimental results from this research. The nonlinear numerical analysis program, which has the functions to perform load-displacement, moment-curvature relations and P-M interactions, was developed on the basis of modified stress-strain relations. The experimental results were compared with analysis results by using this program in CFT and CET circular columns. Several aspects from this research are worth noting.

(1) Comparisons of the experimental and proposed results with the ACI, AISC-LRFD and Eurocode-4 specifications show that the current specifications

are conservative because they don't consider the strength enhancement by confined effects.

(2) Through above comparison of the compressive strength between the CET columns and inner CFT columns, the strength enhancement by the confinement and the effect of cover concrete were evaluated. When the thickness of the cover concrete becomes greater, the maximum compressive strength will become greater. However, in engineering construction, it is not effective that CET columns consisted of the cover concrete more than 30% for the diameter of inner CFT column, due to a brittle failure that the cover concrete was suddenly spalled out.

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